

PECULIARITIES OF PSYCHOPATHOLOGICAL AND NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS IN LATE-LIFE SCHIZOPHRENIA

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ANNOTATION: Relevance. Late-onset schizophrenia often manifests as a slow-progressing form, which delays diagnosis by 10–15 years from its initial stage. Slow schizophrenia is characterized by borderline pathologies, which are often not recognized as symptoms of illness by patients and their relatives, and do not prompt seeking medical care. Additionally, affective (depressive) disorders and high rates of psychoactive substance dependence are frequently observed in slow schizophrenia. Objective. The study aimed to identify the features of higher mental function impairments in patients with late-onset schizophrenia. Materials and Methods. A total of 76 patients (48 women and 28 men), aged 46-68 years (mean 52±5,8), with schizophrenia debuting in late adulthood, were examined. The duration of illness in the main group ranged from 1 to 21 years (mean 7,3±6,12), while the control group (aged 32–59 years) had illness duration from 0.5 to 21 years (mean 7,8±6,7). Clinical-psychopathological, pathopsychological, and neuropsychological methods were applied. Results. An apatho-abulic defect was identified in 38,2% of the main group, and a pseudo-organic defect in 29% of patients. Late-onset schizophrenia patients showed significant deficits in speech, memory, praxis, and thinking compared to the control group ($p<0,05$). Psychocognitive defects varied in type, with apatho-abulic and pseudo-organic variants corresponding to distinct neuropsychological syndromes. Slow schizophrenia also commonly involves a combination of affective, psychopathic-like, and neurocognitive disturbances. Conclusion. The study demonstrated that defect types in late-onset schizophrenia are pathogenetically interconnected and indicate progressive impairments in higher mental functions. The findings allow for localized neurocognitive diagnostics and provide critical guidance for individualized psycho-rehabilitation, including the development of cognitive and social skills.

Keywords: late-onset schizophrenia, slow-progressing schizophrenia, neuropsychological deficit, apatho-abulic defect, pseudo-organic defect, higher mental functions.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПСИХОПАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И НЕЙРОПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЙ НЕГАТИВНЫХ СИМПТОМОВ ПРИ ШИЗОФРЕНИИ В ПОЖИЛОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Актуальность. Шизофрения с дебютом в пожилом возрасте часто проявляется в виде медленно прогрессирующей формы, что задерживает постановку диагноза на 10–15 лет с момента начала заболевания. Медленно прогрессирующая шизофрения характеризуется пограничными патологиями, которые часто не воспринимаются пациентами и их родственниками как признаки болезни и не побуждают обращаться за медицинской помощью. Кроме того, часто наблюдаются аффективные (депрессивные) расстройства и высокая частота зависимости от психоактивных веществ. Цель. Определить особенности нарушения высших психических функций у пациентов с шизофренией с дебютом в пожилом возрасте. Материалы и методы. Было обследовано 76 пациентов (48 женщин и 28 мужчин) в возрасте 46–68 лет (средний возраст $52\pm 5,8$) с дебютом шизофрении в зрелом возрасте. Продолжительность заболевания в основной группе составляла от 1 до 21 года (среднее $7,3\pm 6,12$), в контрольной группе (возраст 32–59 лет) - от 0,5 до 21 года (среднее $7,8\pm 6,7$). Использовались клинико-психопатологические, патопсихологические и нейропсихологические методы. Результаты. Апатико-абулический тип дефекта выявлен у 38,2% основной группы, псевдоорганический дефект - у 29% пациентов. Пациенты с поздним дебютом шизофрении имели значительные нарушения речи, памяти, праксиса и мышления по сравнению с контрольной группой ($p<0,05$). Психокогнитивные дефекты варьировались по типу, апатико-абулический и псевдоорганический варианты соответствовали различным нейропсихологическим синдромам. Медленно прогрессирующая шизофрения часто сопровождается сочетанием аффективных, психопатоподобных и нейрокогнитивных нарушений. Выводы. Исследование показало, что типы дефектов при позднем дебюте шизофрении патогенетически взаимосвязаны и указывают на прогрессирующее нарушение высших психических функций. Полученные данные позволяют проводить локальную нейрокогнитивную диагностику и являются важными для индивидуальной психореабилитации, включая развитие когнитивных и социальных навыков.

Ключевые слова: шизофрения с дебютом в пожилом возрасте, медленно прогрессирующая шизофрения, нейропсихологический дефицит, апатико-абулический дефект, псевдоорганический дефект, высшие психические функции.

**KEKSALIK DAVRIDAGI SHIZOFRENIYADA SALBIY SIMPTOMLARINING
PSIXOPATOLOGIK VA NEYROPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARINI O‘ZIGA XOSLIGI**

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ANNOTATSIYA: Dolzarblik. Keksalik davrida shizofreniya rivojlanishi ko'pincha sekin kechuvchi (past progredient) shaklda namoyon bo'ladi, bu esa tashxisni boshlang'ich bosqichdan 10–15 yilga kechiktiradi. Sekin kechuvchi shizofreniya chegaraviy patologiyalar bilan namoyon bo'lib, bemorlar va ularning yaqinlari tomonidan ko'pincha kasallik belgisi sifatida qabul qilinmaydi va tibbiy yordamga murojaat qilishga sabab bo'lmaydi. Shu bilan birga, sekin shizofreniyada affektiv (depressiv) buzilishlar va psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik yuqori darajada kuzatiladi. Maqsad. Tadqiqotning maqsadi keksalik davrida shizofreniya debuti bilan kechuvchi bemorlarda yuqori aqliy funksiyalarning buzilish xususiyatlarini aniqlashdir. Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqotda 76 nafar bemor (48 ayol va 28 erkak) yosh 46-68 (o'rtacha $52 \pm 5,8$) kiritilgan, ular shizofreniya keksalik davrida debut qilgan. Asosiy guruhda kasallik davomiyligi 1-21 yil (o'rtacha $7,3 \pm 6,12$), nazorat guruhi esa yosh 32-59, kasallik davomiyligi 0,5–21 yil (o'rtacha $7,8 \pm 6,7$) bilan shakllangan. Klinik-psixopatologik, patopsixologik va neyropsixologik usullar qo'llanilgan. Natijalar. Apato-abulik tipdagi defekt 38,2% bemorlarda aniqlangan, pseudo-organik defekt 29% bemorlarda kuzatilgan. Keksalik davrida shizofreniya bilan og'riqan bemorlar nazorat guruhiga nisbatan nutq, xotira, praksiya va fikrlash bloklarida sezilarli pasayishlar bilan farq qilgan ($p < 0,05$). Psixokognitiv defektlar turlicha bo'lib, apato-abulik va pseudo-organik variantlar turli neyropsixologik sindromlarga mos keladi. Shuningdek, sekin shizofreniyada affektiv, psixopatopodobiya va nevrokognitiv buzilishlar kombinatsiyasi ko'p uchraydi. Xulosa. Tadqiqot keksalik davrida shizofreniyada kuzatiladigan defekt turlari patogeneza jihatdan bog'liq bo'lib, aqliy funksiyalarning yuqori darajadagi buzilishlarini aniqlash va individual psixo-reabilitatsiya strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Olingan ma'lumotlar nevrokognitiv defitsitlarni lokal diagnostika qilish va kognitiv hamda ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishda samarali foydalanishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: keksalik davrida shizofreniya, sekin kechuvchi shizofreniya, neyropsixologik defitsit, apato-abulik defekt, pseudo-organik defekt, yuqori aqliy funksiyalar.

Introduction. According to contemporary studies on schizophrenia, the diagnosis of slow-progressing (low-progressive) schizophrenia is often delayed by 10-15 years from the onset of the disorder [1]. This form of schizophrenia is typically characterized by borderline psychopathologies that patients and their relatives frequently fail to recognize as clinical manifestations of the illness, thus delaying seeking professional medical attention [2]. Slow-progressing schizophrenia is also frequently associated with affective disorders, including depressive episodes, and shows a high co-occurrence with psychoactive substance dependence [3-4]. Notably, many healthcare systems, including narcological services, often do not implement a "dual diagnosis" approach, leading to further delays in the identification and management

of these patients [5]. In some cases, schizophrenia remains undiagnosed for years while patients are observed within general medical settings, and a psychiatric evaluation only later establishes the correct diagnosis [6].

Clinically, slow-progressing schizophrenia is difficult to diagnose and is often dominated by negative symptomatology [7]. Neuropsychological investigations that incorporate syndromic analysis and consider the interrelations of higher cognitive functions provide a more coherent understanding of neurocognitive activity in such patients [8]. In adolescence, prior to the onset of affective disorders, psychogenic and psychosocial stressors—such as maternal absence, relocation, or school changes—may contribute to the disease's debut [9]. Early manifestations often include apathetic depression, monopolar affective episodes, or psychopathic-like manic states, which may progress to hypomania [10]. Between ages 15 and 17, many patients begin polysubstance abuse (including alcohol, opiates, cannabinoids, and other psychoactive substances), often concurrent with early subdepressive or hypomanic states [11]. Behavioral disturbances during manic phases can be severe, including psychomotor agitation, alcohol-induced aggression, impulsive behaviors, hypersexuality, and social disinhibition [12]. In depressive phases, patients may deliberately use substances for their perceived antidepressant effects [13].

As the illness progresses, recurrent depressive episodes may occur, sometimes accompanied by schizoaffective episodes or mixed affective states, along with impulsive or creative behaviors [14]. In several cases, heroin dependence and persistent personality changes develop, including psychopathic-like traits or schizoid deficiencies [15]. Female patients with established personality alterations may have children while lacking maternal attachment, leaving childcare to their own parents [16]. Relatives often perceive these patients as difficult, rude, and socially parasitic [17]. Treatment is primarily managed by narcologists, but diagnostic delays are exacerbated by the tendency of families to psychologize the discrepancy between patients' premorbid social or artistic abilities and their subsequent pathological state, rejecting the possibility of a mental disorder diagnosis [18].

Onset during adolescence typically begins with either bipolar affective disorders or recurrent monopolar depression [19]. Bipolar affective disorders progress more rapidly and within 5–6 years may lead to neurocognitive deficits, loss of complex intellectual functions (e.g., inability to continue higher education or postgraduate studies), persistent asthenia, infantilism, and subtle catatonic features [20].

The purpose of the study: the purpose of the work is to determine the features of the violation of high mental functions in patients with schizophrenia with the debut of late life.

Materials and methods. The study involved a total of 76 patients (48 women and 28 men) aged between 46 and 68 years, with an average age of $52 \pm 5,8$ years. These individuals had their first manifestation of schizophrenia occurring in late adulthood, specifically after the age of 45, and they were classified as the main study group. The duration of illness among patients in this group ranged from 1 to 21 years, with a mean duration of $7,3 \pm 6,12$ years, reflecting the heterogeneity of disease progression in late-onset schizophrenia.

To provide a comparative baseline, a control group was formed consisting of 32 patients (24 women and 8 men) whose schizophrenia onset occurred earlier, between the ages of 30 and 44. At the time of assessment, these patients ranged in age from 32 to 59 years. The duration of the illness in the control group varied between 0,5 and 21 years, with an average of $7,8 \pm 6,7$ years, which allowed for a meaningful comparison of disease characteristics and progression between early-onset and late-onset schizophrenia.

A combination of clinical-psychopathological, pathopsychological, and neuropsychological methods was employed to thoroughly assess the patients. Clinical-psychopathological evaluation included careful observation of patients' behavior, affective states, and psychotic symptoms, focusing on both overt manifestations and subtle signs of cognitive and emotional disturbance. Pathopsychological assessments aimed to characterize the underlying psychological mechanisms contributing to observed symptoms and behavioral patterns. Neuropsychological investigations evaluated higher mental functions, including attention, memory, verbal and visual processing, praxis, executive function, and cognitive flexibility, with particular emphasis on deficits associated with late-onset schizophrenia.

This comprehensive, multi-modal approach provided a detailed picture of the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral profiles of patients with schizophrenia in late adulthood. It also allowed the identification of specific patterns associated with late-onset disease, including the interaction between duration of illness, age of onset, and neurocognitive impairment. By comparing the main and control groups, the study aimed to differentiate age-specific features of schizophrenia progression and better understand the implications for diagnosis, prognosis, and rehabilitation planning.

Research results and discussion. In the main group of patients with late-onset schizophrenia, the apato-abulic defect was observed in 29 individuals, accounting for 38,2% of the group, while in the control group this defect was found in 19 patients, representing 59,4%. Patients with late-onset schizophrenia demonstrated significantly lower mean scores across several neuropsychological domains, including "expressive speech," "comprehension of speech and verbal phrases," "auditory-verbal memory," "visual memory," "praxis," and "thinking" ($p < 0,05$). Many patients reported persistent fatigue, drowsiness, and weakness, often requesting to "postpone the conversation" due to limited mental endurance. The decline in the ability to plan, regulate, and control mental activity was particularly prominent among those with apato-abulic impairment. Overall, this defect corresponded to the second variant of neuropsychological syndrome, characterized by disruptions in late-life cognitive regulation, dysfunctions in the prefrontal convexital regions of the frontal lobes, subcortical ganglia, and impaired cortical-subcortical connectivity.

The pseudo-organic defect was identified in 22 patients in the main group (29%) and 6 patients in the control group (18,8%). Patients with this defect showed profound impairments in all higher-order mental functions (VPF). Specifically, significant dysfunctions were noted in "expressive speech," "comprehension of speech and verbal phrases," "auditory-verbal memory," "visual memory," "delayed repetition of sentences and stories," "praxis," "optical-spatial gnosis," "reading," and "thinking" ($p < 0,05$). Symptomatology in this group was polymorphic, and overall impairment of higher cognitive functions was markedly more pronounced and stable compared to the apato-abulic and other defect types. This defect aligned with the third variant of neuropsychological syndrome, reflecting combined dysfunction of the prefrontal convexital formation, subcortical ganglia, and convexital parietal-occipital and temporal cortical regions.

A psychopatho-like personality defect was observed in 21 patients with schizophrenia, representing 23.7% of the main group (18 patients) and 9,3% of the control group (3 patients). Similar to the pseudo-organic defect, disturbances in higher-order mental functions were highly pronounced. In the control group, statistically significant impairments ($p < 0,05$) were recorded in "expressive speech," "speech comprehension," "auditory-verbal memory," "visual memory," "praxis," "optical-spatial gnosis," "acoustic non-verbal gnosis," and "thinking." During tasks such as constructing a short story from pictures, patients in the control group showed greater distractibility from external stimuli. Nevertheless, with supportive

guidance from the examiner, they were able to convey the core meaning of the story. The psychopatho-like defect reflects combined damage to the prefrontal convexital regions of the frontal lobes and subcortical ganglia, with associated dysfunction in the convexital parietal-occipital and temporal areas.

The asthenic defect was the least common, affecting 7 patients in the main group (9,2%) and 4 patients in the control group (12,5%). While all patients exhibited impairments across multiple cognitive domains, the severity was less pronounced in those with asthenic defects compared to other defect types. In particular, deficits in expressive speech, auditory-verbal and visual memory, praxis, gnosis, and thinking were milder in the asthenic defect group.

Overall, these findings highlight that different neuropsychological defect types in late-onset schizophrenia show distinct patterns of cognitive, speech, and behavioral dysfunctions, with implications for individualized diagnosis, treatment planning, and rehabilitation strategies.

The asthenic defect in patients with late-onset schizophrenia was characterized by dysfunctions in the mediobasal and prefrontal convexital regions of the frontal lobes, accompanied by discoordination in the cortical-subcortical networks. This resulted in diminished executive control, impaired planning, and reduced regulation of cognitive and emotional responses.

Among the patients studied, 15 individuals (38,46%) experienced their first-ever hospitalization in a psychiatric facility. However, during the multi-year course of the illness, in the absence of an accurate early diagnosis, 24 patients (61,54%) had previously been admitted to psychiatric and narcological departments, with a majority (66,7%) hospitalized two or more times. In attempts to rationalize these frequent admissions, patients were often misdiagnosed with personality disorders, organic brain pathology, affective disorders, or alcohol and drug dependence, reflecting the diagnostic challenges posed by slow-progressive schizophrenia.

This study identified four principal psychopathological syndromes in the clinic for slow schizophrenia, diagnosed late after disease onset:

Affective syndrome - 20 cases (51.3%)

Somatoform syndrome - 8 cases (20.5%)

Psychopatho-like syndrome - 6 cases (15.4%)

Neurocognitive deficiency syndrome - 5 cases (12.8%)

It was noted that the leading psychopathological syndrome is closely linked to the initial manifestation of the disease.

A pronounced manifestation of neurocognitive deficits was observed in patients whose illness began in preschool age (1-3 years), representing a component of early dysontogenesis, typically manifesting as delayed mental development akin to autism and unusually smooth or blunted emotional reactions. In domestic psychiatry, such cases are classified under schizotypal diathesis. During evaluation, the cognitive repertoire of these patients remained largely unchanged and was identified as a “pseudo-oligophrenic” type of defect. These diagnoses were sometimes first made during military medical examinations.

Comorbid conditions frequently included sub-depressive episodes emerging in adolescence, protective obsessive movements, and social phobia phenomena. Many patients lacked professional skills, were unmarried, and could not engage in low-skilled employment. They lived symbiotically with parents, who often attributed their condition to complications during pregnancy or childbirth, rather than

recognizing a mental disorder. In some instances, parents even financed university studies for patients who were unable to meet academic requirements.

For patients whose illness began during adolescence or adulthood, neurocognitive deficits developed within the framework of a “simplex” syndrome, characterized by gradually increasing intellectual incompetence. The delay in schizophrenia diagnosis was compounded by poor adaptive functioning, limited capacity for independent living, low vocational skills, and orderly conduct in daily life, as well as by the attitudes of relatives, who often either ignored the patient’s difficulties or interpreted them as consequences of perinatal pathology or past traumatic brain injury.

Conclusions. The study shows that defects in late-onset schizophrenia are pathogenetically related, ranging from asthenic dysfunctions to pseudo-organic personality defects, reflecting progressive disturbances in higher mental functions. Detailed neurocognitive profiling allows precise diagnosis and guides psycho-rehabilitation, including cognitive and social skill development.

Syndromic analysis revealed that in prepubertal onset, affective and psychopathic-like disorders were most common ($\approx 15,3\%$), while neurocognitive and somatoform deficits were rarer (7,7% and 5,1%). Adult-onset cases predominantly exhibited affective (35,9%) and somatoform disorders (15,3%).

Early-onset schizophrenia often co-occurred with substance use disorders (70,6%), whereas adult-onset cases showed 57,1% comorbidity with affective disorders and substance use. Prior to accurate diagnosis, patients were frequently misdiagnosed by narcological and general medical services, delaying appropriate psychiatric care.

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